

INTERCULTURALITY AND UNIVERSITY TEACHING: A LOOK AT EDUCATION IN LATIN AMERICA

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ABSTRACT

The Internationalization of Higher Education invites us to deepen the theory of interculturality, which is seen as a plural concept that converges to dialogue between nations. The systematization of intercultural education enables the organization of integrated systems, providing technical knowledge that affects the elaboration of laws and programs. Indeed, intercultural education focuses on the development of global skills, dialoguing with a curriculum whose interdisciplinary treatment reverberates in the epistemological and ontological deepening of knowledge. That said, this work is guided by the decolonial methodology, consisting of a look at Latin American education, promoting reflections on interculturality in higher education in the development of global skills based on principles of teaching, research and extension.

Keywords: Interculturality; Interdisciplinary; Latin American Education.

1. Introduction

From the perspective of contemporary education, the Internationalization of Higher Education (HEI) and, more specifically, interculturality has been the subject of discussions regarding the need to think about the curriculum for the development of global skills. Given the dynamic and multidimensional nature of the internationalization process, actions such as the partnership between academic institutions and the development of interinstitutional projects have become objects of investigation (ALVES; ABBA, 2022), focusing on the principles of teaching, research and extension .

“There is no doubt that internationalization has matured and its importance is being recognized by actors and educational policymakers in all sectors beyond education” (KNIGHT, 2020, p. 11).

With regard to interculturality aligned with the Internationalization of the Curriculum (IoC) process, Knight (2020) argues that the need for internationalization is the result of international and intercultural learning from a process of cooperation and exchange that ends up impacting the way the contents are worked on. Reflecting on interdisciplinary work in HEIs makes it possible to expand learning frameworks (LIMA; ALVES, 2022).

Leask (2015) in *Internationalizing the Curriculum* highlights the importance of IoC present in the most diverse areas of knowledge, thinking about it in an interdisciplinary way from the perspective of internationalization. In this regard, interculturality offers studies focused on cultural aspects of intersocial relationships which, given their complexity, are aligned with teacher training.

Today, reflecting on the role of the university and initial training aims to promote education from an intercultural perspective through the appreciation of languages, a fundamental aspect of culture and intercultural tradition, considering world views to better understand reality.

“The educational process integrates substantive university functions in a global, intercultural, comparative and interdisciplinary dimension that fosters perspectives on global issues in students” (ALVES, 2023, p. 66).

In the context of Latin America, interculturality can help solve problems of integration of people in multicultural societies (MARIN, 2018). In this regard, academic institutions deliberate on the construction of intercultural knowledge, whose impact is on the epistemological and ontological aspects of knowledge.

The international scenario highlights the emergence of the concept of interculturality which, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, notes the growing cultural, linguistic and ethnic diversity, within the scope of greater awareness and awareness regarding cultural plurality and the decolonization movement (UNESCO, 2016).

In this regard, methodologically, interculturality provides the teacher with a differentiated theoretical framework that impacts the student's training and, consequently, their performance in the world as a global citizen. That said, this work is guided by the decolonial methodology that is based on epistemic, theoretical and political science with the purpose of discussing the model of education that is still dominant in the world today (QUIJANO, 2005), where dialogue will be held on interculturality and the internationalization process, promoting

theoretical deepening of interculturality in Latin America and international academic mobility, culminating in reflection on the role of higher education and the principles of teaching, research and extension in promoting global citizenship.

2 Interculturality and the Internationalization Process

The IES internationalization process invites us to deepen the theoretical understanding of interculturality, which will be the subject of discussion in this topic.

The debate on interculturality and intercultural education has been constructed from various perspectives, coming to be seen as a theme that seeks to analyze different points of view, beyond the Eurocentric vision. The study of interculturality has been undertaken, for many years, in the field of linguistic research, culture and communication studies. Repetto (2019, p. 73 – emphasis added) states that,

The perspective of interculturality focuses its attention on visible aspects of culture, such as language and other folklore aspects, and separates society from culture, as if culture had its own reason outside the society in which it lives. This emphasis on “material” aspects of culture and the exacerbation of language led to a predominance of language in hegemonic discourses.

In this sense, interculturality is a plural concept that converges towards dialogue, where education comes to be seen as a space for discussion, articulating ideas, promoting respect and solidarity, taking on various forms and experiences in the face of a globalized world (MARÍN, 2018).

Cultural diversity in the classroom enhances the development of research and extension projects, both from an international and intercultural perspective (LEASK, 2015), where students have the opportunity to experience immersion in different cultures, while at the same time place them as protagonists in the construction of their own knowledge.

In this imperative, Leask (2015) proposes the IoC conceptual map that envisions the curriculum that encompasses the global, regional, local and institutional dimensions, consolidating knowledge through study programs where disciplines seek to develop aspects of professional and civic practice in students . , breaking paradigms in the consolidation of the educational project in society. In this regard, education for the development of global skills dialogues with a curriculum whose interdisciplinary treatment reverberates in the epistemological and ontological deepening of knowledge.

In relation to the curricular aspect “The definitions regarding the curriculum present problematizations that cover a large spectrum of the word, starting with the etymology of the term itself and its most different uses and applications” (MANTOVANI; ALBRECHT, 2017, p. 108).

Next, it is possible to visualize the international dimension of the curriculum based on the conceptual map proposed by Leask (2015).

Figure 1: Conceptual map of Curriculum Internationalization

Source: Leask (2015).

In effect, we can establish that the curricular field is a broad and important area of knowledge in the educational universe, allowing its study from different orientations. The university community is involved in debates about IoC (LEASK, 2021), where teaching and learning rely on the presence of international students on campus and the challenges and opportunities that their diversity brings in classrooms and on campus.

In this process, Leask (2015) makes reference to the study plan and the intercultural perspective through a consolidated pedagogical practice, helping students to develop an understanding of global nature in its scientific, creative, sociocultural, political and economic aspects, preparing them to act as global citizens, meeting social needs and promoting inclusion within plurality.

In dialogue with Betty Leask, Knight (2020) reiterates that the internationalization process has been constantly expanding, presenting different time frames, involving concepts such as interculturality and global citizenship, aligned with the IoC process. Next, there is the evolution of the internationalization process over the last twenty years, which has impacted academic centers (Table 1).

Table 1: Evolution of the Internationalization Process

Contemporary term (last 10 years)	Contemporary term (last 20 years)
Generic Terms	
1) International mobility of programs and providers 2) <i>Soft power</i> 3) Knowledge Diplomacy 4) Smart Internationalization 5) Online Collaborative International Learning	1) Regionalization 2) Planetization 3) Globalization 4) Global citizenship 5) “Green” internationalization 6) Global rankings
Specific Terms	
6) Joint International Universities 7) MOOCs [Massive Open Online Courses] 8) Educational Cities 9) Virtual internships 10) Knowledge Hubs 11) Universities by franchise	7) Regional Educational Centers 8) International Skills 9) Titles Workshops 10) Visa factories 11) Joint, Double, Combined Degree 12) <i>Branding</i> and Status Consolidation

Source: Prepared by the author, based on Knight (2020).

It is necessary to be attentive to the evolution of the internationalization process and its impacts, placing oneself in the position of protagonist in search of strategies in the face of the emerging challenges of contemporary universities (ALVES; ABBA, 2022). The IoC aims to expand the dimensions of teaching as it seeks to cover content whose impact on learning.

Internationalization of the curriculum is the incorporation of international, intercultural and/or global dimensions into the content of the curriculum, as well as into the learning outcomes, assessment, teaching methods and support services of a study program (LEASK, 2015, p. 24 , our translation).²

The systematization of intercultural education makes it possible to organize integrated systems by providing technical knowledge that affects the drafting of laws and programs whose

²⁴“Internationalization of the curriculum is the incorporation of international, intercultural, and/or global dimensions into the content of the curriculum as well as the learning outcomes, assessment tasks, teaching methods, and support services of a program of study”.

effectiveness lies in identifying the main difficulties related to the consolidation of intercultural education in higher education. The reflections promoted remind us of the importance of initial training promoted by universities, covering a diverse and contextualized curriculum. It is necessary to make use of creative teaching, promoting critical reflections and discussions that focus on the pedagogical attitude, providing opportunities for intercultural value and respect.

It is important to highlight that the American continent is the space where modernity was built, as it served as a territory to be explored in the face of the experience of global expansion of European culture (QUIJANO, 2005).

Based on the elucidations proposed by Aníbal Quijano, decolonial thinking aims precisely to propose an education based on citizen empowerment, providing an academic space based on responsibility, flexibility and autonomy, guided by ethical and democratic principles, motivating understanding, solidarity and gratitude towards the social relations, as well as participatory and critical communication.

“The struggles for decolonization refer to the opposition to the colonialist regime, with the objective of ending the colonial regime and establishing the freedom of the people” (VELOSO; SANTANA, 2021, p. 273).

Regarding interculturality, the Group Promoting Interculturality states that we can introduce values, tools and knowledge that refer to respect for peace, human rights and democracy (ACSUR, 2000). Indeed, education is an important means of eliminating stereotypes and, at the same time, promoting the ideals of tolerance and non-violence in promoting peace between nations.

The intercultural movement is surrounded by political processes and intersocial and international relations that have become the focus of analysis of intersubjectivities, following the complex relationships between human groups, aligned with the globalization process. In this regard, global interconnection based on interculturality expands the political strategies that affect the teaching and training of autonomous and protagonist students, moving towards the construction of teaching from a humanist perspective in the promotion of rights. Afterwards, there will be a dialogue on interculturality in Latin America and international academic mobility.

3 Interculturality in Latin America and International Academic Mobility

The American continent has placed itself in a constructivist perspective, with the relative concern of governmental and academic entities with the development of intercultural strategies.

Latin America comprises 20 countries, listed below: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Haiti, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Dominican Republic, Uruguay and Venezuela.

Today, the focus is on the study of intercultural competence in higher education that can be undertaken in the development of intercultural competence (LEASK, 2015). In this regard, Silva (2016, p. 2) states that Mexico,

It was the first country in Latin America to make interculturality official in its educational programs for indigenous people, in partnership with the North American missionary institution Summer Institute of Linguistics – SIL. However, it was only from the 1990s onwards that the perspective of intercultural educational work with indigenous Mexicans became detached from the ideal of homogeneity and civilization.

In Ecuador and Argentina, intercultural educational policy was consolidated in parallel to the regular system, signaling the need to understand interculturality in different voices and different points of view. It is noteworthy that in countries such as Colombia, Guatemala, Costa Rica and Panama, Intercultural Education is managed by national and regional programs (SILVA, 2016).

As an example of this process, the importance of interculturality at the Universidad Nacional de CUYO (UNCuyo) in Argentina is cited, where the university's vision is reflected in the Current Strategic Plan, expressed as follows:

A national university that exercises autonomy with social responsibility, committed to education as a free public good, as a human right and as an obligation of the State and that carries out its functions with inclusion and excellence. An institution that, in the exercise of teaching, research, connection and extension, articulating knowledge and disciplines, engages with society for the common good, in the construction of citizenship and socially fair, environmentally sustainable and territorially balanced development, in context of Latin American and Caribbean regional integration, within the framework of the internationalization processes of higher education. (BENEITONE, 2019, p. 274, our translation)³

Brazil has specific legislation that guarantees educational and intercultural policies that are fundamentally associated with the promotion of education aimed at different ethnicities, guaranteeing the educational rights of indigenous and Afro-descendant populations, providing

³ “A National University that exercises its autonomy with social responsibility, committed to education as public and free, as a human right and as an obligation of the State and that develops its sustainable functions with inclusion and excellence. An institution that, in the integrated exercise of teaching, research, linkage and extension, articulating knowledge and disciplines; engages with society in the achievement of the common good, in the construction of citizenship and in the development of socially fair, environmentally sustainable and territorially balanced, in a context of Latin American and Caribbean regional integration, within the framework of the internationalization processes of the higher education”.

opportunities for the true reach of interculturality supported by economic, epistemic, ethical and political (BRASIL, 1996).

The Brazilian government presents an intercultural educational model for indigenous populations, promoting recognition and respect for different cultures. It is noteworthy that Brazil has specific legislation that guarantees indigenous peoples access to Specific, Differentiated, Intercultural, Bilingual and Multilingual Indigenous Education, the most important of which is the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB) no. 9,394 of 1996 (BRAZIL, 1996).

An example of a Brazilian university that promotes interculturality is the University of International Integration of Afro-Brazilian Lusofonia (UNILAB), a Brazilian federal public higher education institution, based in the states of Bahia and Ceará. This institution hosts students from Africa on undergraduate and postgraduate courses, promoting the exchange of experiences between different cultures, enabling academic mobility, scientific and academic exchange, as well as the exercise of global citizenship.

UNILAB is a federal agency linked to the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Brazil (MEC). Created by Law No. 12,289 of July 20, 2010 and installed in 2011, its objective is to develop research in several areas, contributing to the integration of Brazil with other Portuguese-speaking nations, especially African countries. It is noteworthy that UNILAB is also present in the state of Bahia (UNILAB, 2021).

According to Leask (2015), the fundamental aspects for the development of cultural diversity consist of focusing on student learning, respect for diversity, observation of information related to the specific context and support, enabling meaningful, engaged, flexible and intercultural dialogue. adaptable to different situations.

In the process of expanding intercultural education, international academic mobility emerges as a movement of people, programs, providers, policies, knowledge, ideas, projects and services that cross national borders (KNIGHT, 2020). In America, and more specifically in Brazil, the Science without Borders Program, launched in 2011, financed around 93 thousand full scholarships for Brazilian students abroad between 2012 and 2016, 73% of which were intended for undergraduate studies (BRASIL, 2016).

In Europe and Africa, the European Region Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students functions as a university management program that supports and facilitates the academic mobility of university students and teachers across the world (ERASMUS, 2023).

For Beneitone (2019), interculturality ensures quality inclusion, promoting training for excellence, where aspects such as “Global Citizenship” or “Global Competence” are being requested and which seek critical information in current study plans.

O Latin American Academic Exchange Program is a program that aims to promote the exchange of undergraduate and postgraduate students and teachers in order to enrich their academic, professional and comprehensive training, as well as promote the IES and strengthen cooperation ties between universities (PILA, 2023) . PILA began in 2018, when the first mobility was carried out within the scope of the Program, based on the alliance between the Asociación Nacional de Universidades y Instituciones de Educación Superior (ANUIES), from Mexico, the Asociación Colombiana de Universities (ASCUN), from Colombia, and the Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN), from Argentina.

For Leask (2021), the emphasis on study programs highlights the need to plan and organize opportunities for all students and teachers to develop in-depth knowledge and complete skills with a focus on IoC, based on experiences and activities. Investing in intercultural training is a fundamental condition for strengthening and improving education based on the principles of teaching, research and extension.

The Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988, in its article 207, states that universities enjoy didactic-scientific, administrative and financial and asset management autonomy , and will obey the principle of inseparability between teaching, research and extension (BRASIL, 1988) .

The possibilities and conditions for the academic development of university professors, as they carry out teaching, research and extension favored by the development of interinstitutional projects and partnerships between universities that impact the curriculum, learning outcomes, assessment, teaching methods and services support of a study program (LEASK, 2015). It is noteworthy that among the countries that receive the most educators in this academic mobility process, Hong Kong, Norway, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands (Belgium to the south and Germany to the east), Canada, Australia, Finland and the United States stand out. .

The study developed by Wit *et al* . (2015) *apud* Leask (2021) recognizes the global similarities and differences in the development of internationalization, at regional and national levels, observing common goals and objectives and their impact on university teaching.

Reflecting on the new IoC paradigms, from a conceptual and practical point of view, points to the need for systems to prioritize student learning, from a personal and professional perspective, including spaces for interaction and debates.

Ogude (2007) *apud* Leask (2021) argues that the IoC in South Africa should not only generate new knowledge, but also be related to the preparation of graduates to work globally. Decolonizing the curriculum is an important part of the IoC process for creating spaces and resources to discuss, imagine and conceive alternative cultural worldviews and knowledge systems. For Leask (2015), a decolonized curriculum is capable of examining the forms of dominant approaches to the production and distribution of knowledge.

In Colombia, the Ministry of National Education and the National Quality Assurance System design the set of organizations, policies, strategies and processes whose objective is to guarantee the Internationalization of Higher Education as a quality requirement (DUKOVA et al., 2021).

Driven by programs, student training includes formative, pedagogical and interactional components. Interculturality consists of development and social commitment based on the incorporation of socio-educational practices, strategic planning, the incorporation of a fundamental capacity such as evaluative research from a comparative perspective (BENEITONE, 2019).

Scholars at the University of Hong Kong noted the need for change with development based on the competencies and transformative potential of the IoC. With the support of the Hong Kong government through the University Grants Committee, a professional government advisor was tasked with seeking funding and developing higher education in the region (ZOU, 2021).

At La Trobe University, Australia, all students are invited to think about the curriculum from an international perspective by taking mandatory modules that deepen knowledge of the history, culture and customs of indigenous Australians. To this extent, promoting global citizenship involves interculturality and the development of intercultural competence (LEASK, 2015).

The Maastricht International Business School's mission is to develop educational strategies and practices through the introduction of intercultural business curricular components, involving the study plan, intercultural learning and sustainability, impacting student learning given the need for professional improvement from a perspective global (GREGERSEN-HERMANS; BOONEN, 2021). Given the similarity in the conception of the IoC America, South Africa and Asia, its growing development can be observed in several countries, impacting the curriculum and the way in which the Internationalization of Higher Education is configured on the international scene.

The University of Copenhagen, located in Denmark, from an IoC perspective, presents a high quality in programs that is ensured by a combination of internal and external elements (LAURIDSEN; REHDER, 2021). In collaboration with the faculty and departments responsible for the university regulations, among other things, is the organization and completion of programs, including collaborating and developing the quality of teaching programs.

The University of Guadalajara, Mexico, the mission articulated in the Institutional Development Plan in the period between 2014 and 2030 mentions as an educational project the development of internationalization through the promotion of a set of cognitive and multicultural skills, called global competencies, which enable students to perform in their work, social and cultural contexts, the acquisition of values such as plurality, respect and tolerance (LAURIDSEN; REHDER, 2021).

In this construction, the importance of the internationalization department within universities is cited, which aims to articulate internationalization processes with students, teachers and technical staff of the academic institution, encouraging the development of comparative and international studies in basic and higher education, opening up spaces for academic interactions and dialogues in the educational sphere, outlining paths for promoting global citizenship.

Through the IoC, the United Nations sheds light on interculturality in education, permeating work with importance for the future of humanity through the sharing of experiences and the promotion of Science. A country is able to satisfy the needs of its population when it promotes teaching focused on scientific education, with the resolution of concrete problems that arise in current society, satisfying the needs of its citizens (UNESCO, 2021).

In effect, thinking about global citizenship means providing opportunities for equitable quality education with respect for diversity, promoting inclusion. There is no longer space for Cartesian, disciplinary and fragmented thinking, but the coexistence of space for the development of interdisciplinary and interinstitutional projects is multiplying, giving the curriculum the dimension of a system. Next, the role of higher education in promoting global citizenship will be addressed.

4 Interculturality and the Role of Higher Education in Promoting Global Citizenship

The concept of citizenship emerged in Ancient Greece and was used by different societies over the centuries with varying meanings, having been used to determine the rights relating to individuals in a given location (POZIOMYCK; GUILHERME, 2022). It integrates

central notions of politics, linking it to the idea of individual rights and belonging to a community.

The United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights guarantees the fundamental rights of the human being, such as the dignity and value of the human person, the equal rights of men and women and which decided to promote social progress and better conditions of life (UN, 1948). Legal documents that guide global education bring citizenship as one of the pillars of citizenship training, focusing on aspects such as intellectual autonomy, student protagonism, ethical-scientific production, as well as preparation for the world of work

In this sense, the use of the word citizenship reverberates in reflections on the full exercise of civil and political rights, having been incorporated into the educational curriculum, acting as a tool for social transformation. The potential issue that mobilizes this dialogue is precisely the ever-increasing dimension of globalization and its effects on education and, more specifically, on learning. Curricula that demand global knowledge to meet the needs of the primary, secondary and tertiary sectors, and that end up impacting educational centers.

In this construction, the Internationalization of Higher Education (HEI) includes aspects such as: (1) International education; (2) International cooperation for development; (3) Comparative education; (4) Education by correspondence (KNIGHT, 2020). With academic mobility, global education is aligned with actions and partnerships that have strengthened relations between nations. Interinstitutional projects that arise from mobility at home and across borders are based on a constant need to expand the knowledge that takes place in Sciences and how it reverberates in society.

For Knight (2020), international mobility enables this approach through the creation of international universities based on traditional, satellite and co-founded models, with greater development of interdisciplinary research within universities, international mobility of programs and providers, branding, impacting various subjects that make up the academic curriculum. Terms such as globalization, regionalization and, currently, planetization, seeking to elucidate the importance of promoting a curriculum based on the dimensions of global citizenship.

An inclusive university offers all students the best possible environment for integral development and active and participatory insertion in society. As a university institution, it must seek to meet their distinct academic needs, as well as their sociocultural, economic and family context. Thus, academic activities at all levels and modalities of teaching, scientific research, technological innovation, extension and artistic and cultural production (BRASIL, 1988), where researchers are connected by disciplines and end up developing inherent skills and abilities to

the curriculum component and specific learning as noted below: (1) Natural Sciences and Mathematics characterized as pure sciences due to the rigidity in the application of the scientific method; (2) Applied Sciences such as, for example, engineering; (3) Human Sciences addressed social issues more deeply; (4) Applied Human Sciences such as, for example, education, social work, psychology, among others.

It is reiterated that teaching work must be supported in overcoming the fragmentation of knowledge, allowing democratic and plural coexistence in promoting the understanding of diversity and democratic social practice based on the principles of teaching, research and extension (LIMA; ALVES, 2022) .

In this regard, interdisciplinary work in human sciences, language sciences and natural sciences and mathematics from the perspective of internationalization has become a necessity and, given this finding, preparing students to live harmoniously and globally based on ethics and respect for diversity, makes Science a foundation that is supported by public policies and international organizations such as the UN and UNESCO.

It is imperative to note that, in a subtle way, the internationalization process is imbued with practices that culminate in the expansion of Science based on the principles of teaching, research and extension.

If we define interdisciplinarity as a combination of disciplines, it is worth thinking about the curriculum only in the format of its grid. However, if we define interdisciplinarity as an attitude of boldness and search for knowledge, it is worth thinking about aspects that involve the culture of the place where teachers are trained. Thus, as we expand the analysis of the conceptual field of interdisciplinarity, the possibility arises of explaining its epistemological and praxeological spectrums (FAZENDA, 2013 apud LIMA ; ALVES, 2022, p. 58).

In fact, the idea is not to give ready-made answers, but to build together new paths to be taken in promoting interculturality in line with higher education in education in Latin America. A new epistemology for the promotion of Science is being constructed and which arises in view of the need to establish a new consciousness not only supported by objectivity, but which affirms subjectivity.

In effect, independent and fragmented productions do not promote the formation of global knowledge and, therefore, the interdisciplinary requirement arises as a way of communicating the different objects, where it occurs through the transposition of knowledge (ETGES, 2011).

In the epistemological study, the action focuses on the pedagogical field, occupying increasing space in the IoC expansion processes, a key theme of the most representative events on educator training, in which many scholars sought to define internationalization based on the

relational interpretation with centrality in interdisciplinary understanding. Supported by social development, Science advocates technological advancement in a juxtaposition of actions that reverberate across different sectors and ideological propositions to question real problems.

Mainly promoting the understanding of the problems of scientific construction, the aforementioned educational phenomenon operates the fusion between theory and practice. In this way, the epistemological study of Science guarantees that human beings can consider the importance of a certain scientific knowledge linked to the scope of linguistic, natural and social sciences.

With the demands of the contemporary world, Science provides constructions and methods that focus on awareness, helping to problematize the democratic teaching process. Thinking of society as a network of relationships that are interconnected, interconnected, makes it possible to collectively envision viable solutions to emerging challenges, making the inseparability between the principles of teaching, research and extension a fundamental instrument in promoting Global Citizenship and Interculturality.

5 Final Considerations

Discussions around interculturality in Latin America permeated the discussions, highlighting the importance of the Internationalization of Higher Education (HEI) in promoting intercultural competence, where political processes and intersocial relations become a focus of the analysis of intersubjectivities, following the complex relationships between human groups, as well as the sharing of academic experiences around the world.

In effect, academic mobility enables scientific and academic exchange, focusing on the development of global skills. Thinking about interdisciplinary and intercultural educational spaces that promote respect for diversity, deliberates on the construction of transnational intelligences immersed in the construction of knowledge, focusing on the praxeological construction of knowledge. In fact, much still needs to be done based on the appreciation of culture, knowledge and intercultural traditions, aligned with educational programs, considering world views to better understand their realities.

In fact, the purpose of internationalization is to promote the population's quality of life, whose impact is on geopolitical dimensions and international relations. This understanding leads to the formation of global citizens who start to look at the world and act in the world from a sustainable perspective of caring for themselves and others.

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